

Australian Research Data Commons

Submitting a Data Request to Health Data Australia

Documentation for Data Requesters

ARDC and HeSANDA Node Partners

30 April 2025

Text & infographics only.

Australian Research Data Commons

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15725594

Citation

ARDC Ltd. and HeSANDA Node Partners (2025).
*Submitting a Data Request to Health Data
Australia- Documentation for Data Requesters*

Viewed online at:

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15725594>

Published - 30 April 2025

Acknowledgments

Thank you to our many partners across industry, government, research and community for their contributions

Acknowledgement of Country

We acknowledge and celebrate the First Australians on whose traditional lands we meet, and we pay our respect to their elders past and present.

Cover Images Clockwise

Atthapon - 170206711 / adobestock.com
Gorodenkoff - 402341966 / adobestock.com
DC Studio - 574566575 / adobestock.com
Anela Ramba - 528850160 / adobestock.com
Gorodenkoff - 236237514 / adobestock.com
Kay A - 566595863 / adobestock.com
WavebreakMediaMicro - 132228232 / adobestock.com

<i>Version</i>	<i>Start Date</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Notes</i>
1.0	30/04/2025	ARDC and HeSANDA Node Partners	Original version

Contents

Contents	2
Introduction	3
Pre-request Checklist	4
Steps for Making Data Request	5
Health Portal Authentication Service	5
Dataset Requested Tab	7
Applicant Details Tab	8
Project Administration Tab	9
Project Design Tab	10
Project Outputs Tab	12
Ethics Tab	13
Example Data Request Form	14
Scenario 1: Jill the PhD Student	14
STEP 1: DATASET REQUESTED	15
STEP 2: APPLICANT DETAILS	15
STEP 3: PROJECT ADMINISTRATION	16
STEP 4: PROJECT DESIGN	17
STEP 5: ETHICS	19
Scenario 2: Matt the Senior Post Doc	20
STEP 1: DATASET REQUESTED	20
STEP 2: APPLICANT DETAILS	21
STEP 3: PROJECT ADMINISTRATION	21
STEP 4: PROJECT DESIGN	22
STEP 5: ETHICS	23
Glossary	24

Introduction

This is a supplementary resource for researchers submitting a formal request for access to a dataset listed on the Health Data Australia (HDA) platform. This documentation was developed as part of a work package for HeSANDA.

The process for finding and accessing data on the HDA platform can be summarised as follows:

Before using this resource, we recommend starting with the following resources available on the ARDC website:

1. **How to Access Data** (Top right of the Health Data Australia home screen)

<https://researchdata.edu.au/health/>

This provides a streamlined overview of the process

2. **Services User Guides – Health Data Australia**

<https://documentation.ardc.edu.au/hda/general-information>

Explains what Health Data Australia (HDA) is (a catalogue) and what it's not (a data repository) Details the data request process, including how to search for datasets, understand their format and content, and save searches

This Guide clarifies the requirements of the 'Access the data' process, explaining the rationale behind each field and providing practical examples to help researchers complete requests accurately, minimising misinterpretation and follow-up queries.

Pre-request Checklist

Before you make a data request through HDA, there are some things you should know and have ready to provide during the request process. Use this checklist to make sure you have what you need so that your data request goes smoothly.

■ ***Have you reviewed the Data Sharing Statement?***

The HDA catalogue entry for each dataset includes important information about what data is available and under what conditions. This 'Data Sharing Statement' is drawn from the ANZCTR record for the clinical trial and appears in the 'Source Study' section of the HDA record. Be sure to review these details to make sure they match your data request requirements.

■ ***Are you an employee, research student or affiliate of an Australian University or research institution?***

To make a request for data through Health Data Australia, you will need to log in using Australian Access Federation (AAF) authentication, which is only available to staff and students of research institutions. If you work for another type of organisation, such as a health service, consider asking a University-affiliated collaborator involved in the project to make the request.

■ ***Do you have an ORCID?***

You will be asked to provide your ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) if you have one. If you do not have an ORCID, you can obtain one instantly by registering on the ORCID website - <https://orcid.org/register>.

ORCID is a useful, free, unique, persistent identifier (PID) that uniquely identifies authors and contributors of scholarly communication and is a useful thing for all researchers to have.

■ ***Why are you making this data request and how do you plan to use the data?***

Throughout the expression of interest form, you will be asked to briefly explain why you are requesting the dataset and provide some general information about your proposed project, such as aims, hypotheses, expected outputs and outcomes. It will help to have your grant application, project proposal or similar document handy to provide this information. If you need assistance to determine the methodology to use, see [Secondary Use of Clinical Trials Data in Health Research: A Practical Guide](#).

■ ***Have you thought about conflicts of interest?***

Are there any conflicts of interest you may need to declare in relation to your research study? Think about any personal or professional relationships or affiliations with other institutions or commercial entities.

■ ***What is the status of your Ethics application?***

All secondary research using health data requires HREC approval. You can make a data request without having HREC approval, but be prepared to provide information on the current status of your application.

Steps for Making Data Request

Once you have browsed the health dataset of your interests and wish to use it for your own research project, click the 'Access the data' button on your chosen dataset, which redirects you to the Health Portal Authentication Service.

 Access the data

You can initiate a request for access through Health Data Australia (HDA) by filling in an Expression of Interest (EOI) form after logging in with your AAF credentials.

HDA offers a streamlined and user-friendly process for requesting access to all the health datasets available. Upon submitting your request, you will receive automated email notifications to keep you informed of any updates regarding your request. Additionally, you can conveniently track the progress and status of your request by accessing your MyHDA profile page.

To request datasets from HDA, you must be a registered user of the service. You can become a registered user using our [Health Portal Authentication Service](#) if you are affiliated with Universities or research institutions that are part of the Australian Access Federation (AAF).

Once you have located a dataset you would like to use, click the [Access the data] button and complete a Data Request and supply details of your proposed use of the data. There are 6 tabs to complete:

1. [Dataset Requested](#): why you are requesting the dataset
2. [Applicant Details](#): your organisation and contact details
3. [Project Administration](#): project title, start and end date, and funding sources
4. [Project Design](#): overview of project aims, hypotheses, outcomes, and data security
5. [Project Outputs](#): intended outputs and arrangements for Intellectual Property
6. [Ethics](#): status of ethics approval for your research

Details of each tab are provided in the rest of this guideline document.

Health Portal Authentication Service

Anyone can search the Health Data Australia (HDA) platform, but only researchers from universities or research institutions that are part of the Australian Access Federation (AAF) can request access to data. AAF is a national authentication system that verifies a researcher's affiliation with a subscribing institution and allows them to log in using their institutional credentials. View [a list of AAF subscribers](#).

Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) recognise that clinician researchers not affiliated with an academic institution are currently unable to request datasets from HDA. ARDC is actively exploring alternative authentication methods to enable access for non-University researchers to log in to HDA.

Task	Instructions
Log In	<p>Click on the 'AAF' button on the right side: this will take you to the Australian Access Federation authentication platform.</p> <p>Do not use the left side of the panel, as direct username and password login won't fulfil HDA's authentication requirement.</p>
Find your institution	<p>Choose your institution from the AAF list and follow your usual institutional login process, for example, your staff identification number and password.</p> <p>You are now on the 1st tab of the HDA request form, Dataset Requested.</p> <p>Fields with a red asterisk are mandatory.</p>

Dataset Requested Tab

Dataset Requested	Applicant Details	Project Administration	Project Design	Project Outputs	Ethics
Dataset DOI: *	<input type="text" value="http://doi.org/10.25910/WRAZ-3884"/>				
Dataset Title: *	<input type="text" value="OPTimising IMMunisation Using Mixed schedules (OPTIMUM): comparing allergic outcom"/>				
Data Access Requirement: *	<input type="text" value="Please describe why you require access to the dataset"/>				
Bio Sample:	<input type="text" value="Please describe any biological sample you require access to."/>				
<input type="button" value="Save"/> <input type="button" value="Next"/>					

The 'Dataset DOI' and 'Dataset Title' fields will be pre-filled based on the dataset you have selected to access.

Complete the remaining fields as follows:

Task	Instructions
Data Access Requirements	<p>Provide a brief statement explaining why you are requesting this dataset, including an overview of the type of secondary research you will be undertaking.</p> <p>Examples include evidence synthesis, secondary analyses, verification of scientific findings, or leveraging existing datasets for educational or methodological purposes.</p> <p>For more details on these categories, refer to this resource. Secondary Use of Clinical Trials Data in Health Research: A Practical Guide</p> <p>Do not include details such as aims, hypotheses, or methodology here; these should be provided in the Project Design tab of this request form.</p>
Bio Sample	<p>If the HDA catalogue entry for this dataset indicates that biospecimens are available, specify the samples you wish to access for your research project.</p> <p>Leave this field blank if you are not requesting biospecimens.</p>

Applicant Details Tab

If you have logged in using Australian Access Federation (AAF), some fields such as 'Requesters Name' and "Email" will be filled out automatically.

Fill out the remaining required fields accordingly.

Researcher Name	Include your full name here
Organisation Name	If you are working with a team that spans across multiple institutes or you are affiliated with multiple institutes, please include the institute where the majority/bulk of the analysis, conceptualisation and decision making will take place.
Position	Include the position association with the affiliation above
Email	Include the email of the primary correspondent.
ORCID	<p>ORCID, which stands for Open Researcher and Contributor ID, is a free, unique, persistent identifier (PID). ORCID uniquely identifies authors and contributors of scholarly communication.</p> <p>If you do not have an ORCID, registration is quick and easy. Please register on their website - https://orcid.org/register - to instantly obtain an ORCID. You can use this here.</p>
Add project participant	If you are not the Project Lead or Principal/Chief Investigator for the proposed project (for example, you are a PhD student or Research Assistant), please also add the details of the Project Lead or Supervisor as an additional Project Participant.

Project Administration Tab

Dataset Requested	Applicant Details	Project Administration	Project Design	Project Outputs	Ethics
<p>Project Identifier:* <input type="text" value="Your project's unique identifier"/> ?</p> <p>Project Title:* <input type="text"/> ?</p> <p>Start Date:* <input type="text"/> ?</p> <p>End Date:* <input type="text"/> ?</p> <p>Funding Sources:* <input type="text"/> ?</p> <p>Conflict of Interest/Relevant Disclosures: <input type="checkbox"/> ?</p> <p>Previous Save Next</p>					

Project Identifier	<p>Enter the identifier assigned to the proposed project by your institution, for example, by the Research Office or Department administration.</p> <p>If you don't have an institutional identifier, please enter zero in this field.</p>
Project Title	<p>This is the current or working title of your project, recognising that it may change over time.</p>
Start and End Dates	<p>Provide the planned start and end date of your project, assuming your data request is successful.</p>
Funding Sources	<p>Provide information about the sources of funding for your project, including grant funding you have received or applied for, internal (institutional) funding, or commercial sources.</p>
Conflicts of Interest	<p>Use this section to disclose any conflicts of interest or other information that may be important when considering your data request.</p> <p>For example, you should provide information about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concurrent or joint appointments at more than one institution; • any personal or professional relationships with the researchers whose dataset you are requesting access to; • Association with organisations other than your employing institution, including commercial entities such as a pharmaceutical, biomedical, AI/ML or other technology

	<p>companies. An association could be membership of a board or advisory committee, consultancies, or receipt of funds, services or equipment.</p> <p>This requirement is based on the responsibilities of researchers in relation to conflicts of interest set out in the NHMRC guide, “Disclosure of interests and management of conflicts of interest: A Guide supporting the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research” (2019). Declaring actual and potential conflicts of interest is important for maintaining the integrity of research and ensuring trust in researchers.</p>
--	---

Project Design Tab

Dataset Requested	Applicant Details	Project Administration	Project Design	Project Outputs	Ethics
			<p>Project Background or Rationale:*</p> <p>Please describe the background or rationale of the project</p> <p>Project Aims:*</p> <p>Please describe the aims of the project</p> <p>Project Hypotheses:*</p> <p>Please describe the project hypotheses</p> <p>Project Outcomes:*</p> <p>Please describe the project outcomes</p> <p>Data Security Strategy:*</p> <p>Please describe the project data security strategy</p> <p>Previous Save Next</p>		

Project Background or Rationale	<p>Please complete the details of your proposed project. In particular, please outline what you intend to do with the data that you have requested.</p> <p>It might be useful to include what data fields that you are requesting.</p> <p>For example, if the data set includes a data dictionary, please include the field names as they appear in the data dictionary</p>
Project Aims	<p>Please include a summary of the aims/objectives of the research project that should allow the data holder to make an informed decision.</p>

	<p>Pay particular attention to highlighting why and how you believe that the requested dataset will contribute to your research project.</p>
Project Hypothesis	<p>Please clearly highlight the hypotheses that you have formulated for your research project.</p> <p>In particular, it would be very helpful to the data provider if you could stress how your new hypotheses will complement the hypotheses from the data set, especially if you intend to request IPD.</p> <p>If you need assistance in formulating your hypothesis, see “Secondary Use of Clinical Trials Data in Health Research: A Practical Guide” for support.</p>
Project Outcomes	<p>Please describe the intended project outcomes.</p> <p>Some examples of outcomes are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Novel research ■ Extending the research findings ■ Replicating a research finding (from the original trial) ■ Exploring incidental findings ■ etc
Data Security Strategy	<p>Please clearly outline the steps that you will undertake to keep the data secure if your request is granted. In particular, you should clearly outline a data management plan that explicitly describes the data access plan, storage and, importantly, the disposal of the dataset at the end of the project.</p> <p>If your institution has a data management guideline, especially pertaining to data security, please include a link to it in this section if possible.</p>

Project Outputs Tab

Dataset Requested
Applicant Details
Project Administration
Project Design
Project Outputs
Ethics

Output Type:* ?

Output Title:* ?

IP Arrangements:* ?

Estimated Completion Date:* 📅 ?

Add a project output ↕

Previous
Save
Next

Provide information here about the expected outputs from your project. If unsure of the outputs, type ‘To be confirmed’ as this is a required field.

Outputs could include journal publications, study protocol, data dictionary, Data Management Plan, Statistical Analysis Plan. If the

Output Type	<p>Please include any expected output(s) for this research project. If you are unsure, please write: “To be confirmed” as this is a required field. However, you are well advised to provide a relevant output type as this will likely hasten the approval process.</p> <p>Examples of outputs are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Scientific publication or report ■ Research dataset (to complement the existing dataset) ■ Training material or tutorial ■ etc
Output Title	<p>Please provide a title for the intended output, while acknowledging that this may change in the future</p>
IP Arrangements	<p>Please include details of any obligations or commitments relating to the intellectual property (IP) in the research output. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ does the project funding agreement include any requirements for ownership or use of the IP? ■ will the project output(s) be used by a sponsor, partner or collaborator for commercial purposes, such as AI development? <p>If there are no specific IP arrangements, please type ‘Not Applicable’.</p>
Estimated Completion Date	<p>This can be your best estimate, understanding that project time frames can change.</p>

Ethics Tab

Dataset Requested
Applicant Details
Project Administration
Project Design
Project Outputs
Ethics

Do you have ethics approval?* Yes No ?

Upload Ethics Approval no file selected ?
(Maximum file size is 10M)

Will the project report on indigenous or vulnerable populations?* Yes No ?

Do you have additional information not captured elsewhere? ?

CERTIFICATION

I certify that all the information provided are true and correct to the best of my ability*

I authorise ARDC and the data custodian to use the information in this form ONLY for the purpose(s) relevant to this request*

Previous
Save
Submit

All secondary research using health data will require HREC approval. Ethical approval for secondary research helps maintain ethical standards, protects participants and ensures responsible use of existing data.

It is acceptable to initiate the data access request without ethics approval, however, you must obtain ethics approval before data is released, accessed and analysed. It is important to be transparent about your approval status throughout the process

Do you have ethics approval?	At the time of making the data access request, please state if you have HREC approval, 'Yes' or 'No'. If no is selected, be aware that you will require full ethical approval prior to accessing or analysing the data.
Upload Ethics approval	If you have obtained HREC approval prior to submitting the data access request, please upload the approval letter.
Will the project report on Indigenous or vulnerable populations?	Noting this information will assist the primary researcher to ensure proper ethical oversight and culturally appropriate research practices.
Do you have additional information not captured elsewhere?	Select this box if you would like to provide additional details on obtaining ethical approval or if there are unique considerations about data custody and use.

Example Data Request Form

Scenario 1: Jill the PhD Student

Jill is in the second year of her PhD candidacy and is conducting trials to test the efficacy of an exercise therapy developed by her PhD supervisor, Henry.

Keen to broaden her research project scope and build her skills, Henry suggests that she conducts a meta-analysis on other exercise therapies for neurodegenerative diseases, to see how they compare with her results.

She uses the Health Data Australia platform and uses the search function to discover clinical trial data sets available to accelerate her research.

While exploring the metadata catalogue, she finds many datasets she could potentially include in her study. There is one study that is closely aligned with her research, which she wishes to pursue:

She clicks on the “Access the data” icon and authenticates herself via the AAF login using her university email address to proceed to the data request.

Her data request to the data custodian appears as follows:

STEP 1: DATASET REQUESTED

Data Requested	
DOI (<i>auto-filled</i>)	http://doi.org/10.26180/23713503
Dataset Title (<i>auto-filled</i>)	A pilot randomised controlled trial of a vestibular-stimulation, isometric exercise machine to manage symptoms of Parkinsonism
Reason for Request (<i>Jill was able to use figure provided in Secondary Use of Clinical Trials Data in Health Research: A Practical Guide showcasing the different types of methods that could be used with secondary clinical trials data</i>)	The data is required as I am conducting a meta-analysis (secondary analysis).
Bio Sample (<i>There were no bio-specimens included in this study</i>)	Not required

STEP 2: APPLICANT DETAILS

Applicant Details	
Research Name (<i>auto-filled</i>)	Jill Citizen
Researcher email	z3225897@fauxMRI.edu.au
Researcher Position	PhD Student
Researcher ORCID (<i>Jill did not have an ORCID, so she went to the website and registered for one, which took about 10 mins</i>).	3333-3333-3333
Researcher Organisation	Faux Medical Research Institute

As her PhD Supervisor (Henry), is also involved in the research project, she included him as a project participant. In this section, none of the fields were auto-filled, so she manually filled the following herself, and confirmed details with Henry:

Additional Project Participant	
Additional Research Name	Henry Freeman
Researcher email	r.freeman@fauxMRI.edu.au
Researcher Position	Associate Professor
Researcher ORCID <i>(Jill needs to confirm this with Henry before proceeding).</i>	5555-5555-5555
Researcher Organisation	Faux Medical Research Institute

STEP 3: PROJECT ADMINISTRATION

Jill is initially hesitant to complete these fields, as she had not thought about things like ‘project titles’ or ‘descriptions’ and had no clear start and end dates. But Henry assures her that nothing included here is ‘set in stone’. He clarifies that the data provider receiving the request would recognise that these fields were preliminary and subject to change as her research developed. The purpose of including this information is to offer the data provider a starting point for the project's scope and direction.

The important factor here is to be simple yet descriptive for the data custodian to see what is planned for the dataset.

Project Details	
Project Administrative	
Project Identifier <i>(Jill was originally unsure what to include here. Henry tells her that she can include any pre-existing ID number assigned to their project. Fortunately, their institute</i>	ACEF13579

<i>provided their project with a unique identifier, which he told her to use.</i>	
Project Title	Studying the efficacy of various exercise therapies to neurodegenerative disease
Start Date	01/03/2025
End Date <i>(She decides to include the date she plans to submit her thesis)</i>	25/02/2026
Funding Sources	MRFF grant
Conflict of Interest/Relevant disclosures <i>(Henry confirmed there were no conflict of interests in this case)</i>	Nil

STEP 4: PROJECT DESIGN

Similar to step 3 – Jill decides that the best course of action here is to be simple, yet descriptive so the data custodian receives the clearest interpretation of her work and what is required.

Project Design	
Background or Rationale	Exercise therapy has been shown to improve outcomes for patients with age-related neurodegenerative disease, such as Parkinson's disease. Exaggerated muscle flow therapy (EMFT) developed by Freeman, et al (2018) has shown great promise in physical therapy. To gain a greater understanding of the efficacy of EMFT, we wish to compare our results with other various exercise therapies.
Aims	To assess the efficacy of various exercise therapies in the treatment of 'Faux disease' and compare that with the efficacy of the exercise therapy we have developed (EMFT).

Hypotheses	The efficacy of EMFT is just as impactful as other already developed and utilised exercise therapies.
Outcomes and Endpoints	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To determine the efficacy of EMFT 2. To compare the impact of EMFT with other existing exercise therapies
Data Security Strategy	All data will be stored in the internal servers at FauxMRI, and will follow protocol according to FauxMRI ethics protocol.
Project Outputs	
Output Type	Journal Publications
Output Title (<i>Henry reminds Jill that the title is not 'set in stone', and it is understood that it can change based on the results of the secondary analyses. He advises her to write a title that describes what she hopes to gain from obtaining the dataset.</i>)	The efficacy of various exercise therapies of neurodegenerative disease progression.
IP Arrangements	For research use only
Output Completion Date	25/02/2026

Jill notices that you can add multiple outputs and decides to include her thesis.

Project Outputs (2)	
Output Type	PhD Thesis
Output Title	Investigating the Therapeutic Potential of Exercise Modalities in Neurodegenerative Diseases: A Clinical Trial-Based Assessment of Efficacy and Disease-Modifying Outcomes
IP Arrangements	For research use only
Output Completion Date	25/02/2026

STEP 5: ETHICS

Although Jill realises that ethics approval hasn't yet been obtained for this particular project, Henry explains that it wouldn't be necessary at this stage, though they would need ethics approval before starting the secondary analysis, and before any results are published.

Ethics Information	
Ethics Approval Obtained	No, but we will attain ethics approval once we receive the data and start analysis.
Ethics Approval File	N/a
Will the project report on Indigenous or vulnerable populations? <i>(Jill recognises the possibility that some Indigenous and vulnerable populations may be represented in the data, but there wouldn't be explicit documentation that explains how this information is captured, therefore, does not need to acknowledge this potential in the data request.</i>	This information was not captured.
Additional information	N/A

Jill submits her data request and receives a PDF copy of the request in her inbox as confirmation. When the data provider receives the request, she will receive updates via email of its progress. She also knows that if she wishes to edit or withdraw this request at an appropriate time, she can do so via MyHDA on the HDA platform.

Scenario 2: Matt the Senior Post Doc

Matt has spent many years testing the efficacy of a medication in randomised controlled trials and feels that he has made a significant breakthrough.

He wants to compare with other clinical trials testing similar medications to see if:

1. Other studies could broaden the scope of his research (i.e. evidence synthesis)
2. Replicate studies have already been conducted (Reproducibility, replication, and validation)

After navigating the Health Data Australia platform, he finds a study and proceeds to request the data:

He clicks on the “Access the data” icon and authenticates himself via the AAF login using his university email address to proceed to the data request.

His data request to the data custodian appears as follows:

STEP 1: DATASET REQUESTED

Data Requested	
DOI <i>(auto-filled)</i>	http://doi.org/10.26187/VC6S-S708
Dataset Title <i>(auto-filled)</i>	REDUCE: Does Antipsychotic Dose Reduction Lead to Better Functional Recovery in First Episode Psychosis: A Randomised Controlled Trial

Reason for Request (<i>Matt was able to use the figure provided in “Secondary Use of Clinical Trials Data in Health Research: A Practical Guide” showcasing the different types of methods that could be used with secondary clinical trials data</i>)	The data is required as I am conducting <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence synthesis Reproducibility, replication, and validation
Bio Sample (<i>There were no bio-specimens included in this study</i>)	Not required

STEP 2: APPLICANT DETAILS

Applicant Details	
Researcher Name (<i>auto-filled</i>)	Matthew Quinn
Researcher email	m.quinn@UnREALMRI.edu.au
Researcher Position	Senior Research Fellow
Researcher ORCID (<i>Luckily, Matt had already registered for an ORCID and could populate this field with it by checking the number in his ORCID account</i>)	2222-2222-2222
Researcher Organisation	UnREAL Medical Research Institute

STEP 3: PROJECT ADMINISTRATION

Project Details	
Project Administrative	
Project Identifier (<i>Fortunately, Matt has registered the study and has a Research</i>)	XX234XX

<i>Activity Identifier (RAiD) - more information</i>	
Project Title	Testing the impacts of various medications on mental health disorders.
Start Date <i>(Matt decides to use the start and end dates of the grant he just received as an indicator of the timeline to the data provider)</i>	31/01/2025
End Date	31/01/2027
Funding Sources	NHMRC Ideas grant
Conflict of Interest/Relevant disclosures <i>(Matt has worked previously with the people listed as the creators of the dataset, and thought it would be a good idea to disclose that here)</i>	The data requester has previously worked with the data providers. The data requester is open to collaborating with the data provider on the current project outcomes.

STEP 4: PROJECT DESIGN

Project Design	
Background or Rationale <i>(Matt writes a simple and succinct description of his study)</i>	Our studies testing the effects of the drug, FKE, have found a significant reduction of symptoms in patients. Our next step is to compare the efficacy of FKE with drugs with similar mechanisms to see how impactful FKE is on patient outcomes.
Aims	To compare the effects and efficacy of FKE with drugs with similar mechanisms on patient outcomes.
Hypotheses	The efficacy of FKE is significantly greater on patient outcomes when compared to similar drugs.
Outcomes and Endpoints	1. To compare the efficacy of FKE to other drugs with similar mechanisms.

	2. To determine the efficacy of FKE compared to other drugs with similar mechanisms.
Data Security Strategy	All data will be stored in the internal servers at UnREALMRI, and will follow protocol according to UnREALMR ethics protocol.
Project Outputs	
Output Type	Publication
Output Title	
IP Arrangements <i>(Matt also discloses here that he is open for collaboration, as he has worked with this team previously)</i>	For research use only. The data requester is open for collaboration with the data providers (please contact me if interested)
Output Completion Date	31/01/2027

STEP 5: ETHICS

Ethics Information	
Ethics Approval Obtained <i>(Matt has planned on conducting a secondary analysis since the start of this project and has already included this in his original HREC application - with the help from resources found from CT:IQ, including the InFORMED PICF)</i>	Yes
Ethics Approval File	HREC - 112233
Will the project report on Indigenous or vulnerable populations?	No
Additional information	No

Matt submits her data request and receives a PDF copy of the request in his inbox as confirmation. When the data provider receives and processes the request, Matt will receive updates via email of its progress. He can withdraw the request at any time via MyHDA or the HDA platform.

Australian Research Data Commons

Glossary

Populate Glossary here and we'll include it at finalisation -

[WP2 - Guidance Documentation Glossary](#)

Australian Research Data Commons

CONTACT

- ardc.edu.au
- +61 3 9902 0585
- contact@ardc.edu.au

FOLLOW

- [australian-research-data-commons](https://www.linkedin.com/company/australian-research-data-commons)
- [ARDC_AU](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCARDC_AU)
- [subscribe to our newsletter](#)

Australian Government

ARDC is enabled by NCRIS